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Energy Relations Between Türkiye-Azerbaijan within the Framework of Neorealism Theory Neorealizm Teorisi Çerçevesinde Türkiye- Azerbaycan Arasındaki Enerji İlişkileri

ABSTRACT

Türkiye prioritizes the South Caucasus in its foreign policy to meet its rising energy demand, strengthen its energy security, and realize its long-term strategy of becoming an energy corridor. In this context, relations with Azerbaijan, in particular, play a critical role. Analyzing the energy relationship between the two countries constitutes the main objective of this article. This study examines the importance of the ties established between Azerbaijan and Türkiye, utilizing content analysis to better understand the dynamics in this context. Furthermore, it aims to analyze the energy relationship between Türkiye and Azerbaijan from a neorealist perspective. Within the scope of the research, energy cooperation between the two countries is analyzed in light of key concepts such as national interests, balance of power, security, the structure of the system, regional and global power balances, efforts to balance energy supply and demand, potential conflict scenarios, and elements of competition. At this point, it is concluded that neorealist theory, which acknowledges the anarchic nature of the international system and emphasizes the importance of both increasing power and ensuring security for states, offers a suitable perspective on the subject. Thus, it is believed that examining the energy relationship between Türkiye and Azerbaijan within a theoretical framework will provide an additional contribution to the discipline.

Keywords: Energy Security, Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Neorealism

ÖZET

Türkiye yükselen enerji talebini karşılamak, enerji güvenliğini güçlendirmek ve uzun vadede bir enerji koridoru olma stratejisini hayata geçirmek için Güney Kafkasya'yı dış politikasında öncelikli bir konuma taşımaktadır. Bu doğrultuda bölge ülkelerinden özellikle Azerbaycan ile ilişkiler kritik bir rol oynamaktadır. İki ülke enerji ilişkisinin analizi bu makalenin temel amacını oluşturmaktadır. Bu çalışma Azerbaycan ve Türkiye arasındaki kurulan bağların önemini ele alarak, bu bağlamdaki dinamikleri daha iyi anlamak amacıyla içerik analizinden faydalanmaktadır. Ayrıca Türkiye ve Azerbaycan arasındaki enerji ilişkisinin neorealist bir perspektifle ele alınarak incelenmesi hedeflenmektedir. Araştırma kapsamında iki ülke arasındaki enerji iş birliği, ulusal çıkarlar, güç dengesi, güvenlik, sistemin yapısı, bölgesel ve küresel güç dengeleri, enerji arzı ve talebi dengeleme çabaları, potansiyel çatışma senaryoları ve rekabet unsurları gibi kilit kavramlar ışığında analiz yapılmaktadır. Bu noktada uluslararası sistemin anarşik bir yapıya sahip olduğunu kabul eden ve devletler açısından hem gücü artırmanın hem de güvenliği sağlamanın önemine vurgu yapan neorealist kuramın, konuya uygun bir perspektif sunduğu sonucuna ulaşılmıştır. Böylece Türkiye ve Azerbaycan enerji ilişkisinin teori çerçevesinde incelenmesinin disipline ek bir katkı sağlayacağı düşünülmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Enerji Güvenliği, Türkiye, Azerbaycan, Neorealizm

1. INTRODUCTION

Energy is one of the most fundamental resources for the continuity of human life, so it is necessary to ensure access to the required energy in an affordable, reliable, and uninterrupted manner. The demand for energy is increasing worldwide due to the growing population and economies that require sustainable growth. Therefore, the reliable supply of energy has become one of the top priorities for countries in terms of both the continuity of social life and economic development.

The energy supply system shapes the international system through the interaction between supplier countries that control and trade energy resources and consumer countries that demand these resources. As a result, interaction between energy-supplying and energy-consuming countries is increasing. As the need for energy grows daily, the interdependence between energy-producing and energy-consuming countries increases at the same rate. In this situation, producer and wealthy countries that hold energy reserves use energy as a power factor against energy-dependent countries. To break free from this dependency, consumer countries such as Türkiye can resort to energy diversification or seek new energy suppliers (Güneş & Arslan, 2018: 33).

Türkiye, which is highly dependent on foreign energy sources, has sought to develop opportunities for cooperation with Azerbaijan, a supplier country with rich energy resources, in order to close its gaps in this area and place its energy needs on a more sustainable footing. On the other hand, Azerbaijan, which is in a highly advantageous position in terms of energy resources, aims to gain economic benefits from regional cooperation and strengthen its influence on the global stage by increasing energy exports. In this context, when shaping their energy policies, states have either adopted an aggressive stance, aiming to gain direct access to resources, or have preferred cooperation, seeking to produce joint solutions. Thus, states' aggressive or cooperative approaches to energy policy have been shaped by their national interests. These developments have paved the way for security dilemmas to emerge in regions rich in energy resources and for new collaborations to form around these dilemmas. Neo-realist theory provides an important tool for understanding the energy policies of states in this context (İren & Atlığ, 2022: 326). Moreover, this theoretical approach allows us to explain how energy policies are shaped and their role within the international system by focusing on the balance of power, national security, and the interests of states. Furthermore, the neo-realist perspective enables comprehensive assessments in analyses of states' decision-making processes regarding energy policies and global energy competition. Generally speaking, the energy policies of both countries are intertwined with certain arguments of neo-realism. This study seeks to answer the following questions: How are energy relations between Türkiye and Azerbaijan assessed by neo-realism? What is the importance of Azerbaijan in terms of T's energy security? In its energy relations with Azerbaijan, is Türkiye an energy hub or an energy transit country? In this regard, the study uses a literature review highlighting the assumptions of neorealism theory as a theoretical framework.

The research is primarily based on qualitative research methods, and in this context, the document analysis method has been preferred. Written sources containing information related to the subject have been examined in detail in the study. Data obtained from primary and secondary sources have been analyzed, and a comprehensive academic literature review has been conducted. Furthermore, the study imposed a time constraint on the topic of energy security in Turkish foreign policy. Within this framework, Türkiye-Azerbaijan energy relations were examined within the context of the period spanning from Azerbaijan's independence in 1990 to the present day. The geographical scope of the study was defined as the South Caucasus region, including Azerbaijan and Georgia.

In the energy security literature, a significant portion of the studies on the South Caucasus, an important region in terms of energy resources, and the policies related to the resources in this region consist of Türkiye and Azerbaijan-focused research. In recent years, studies on Türkiye-Azerbaijan relations have increased significantly in Turkish literature. The Second Karabakh War and subsequent developments have greatly increased interest in energy relations between Türkiye and Azerbaijan and given new impetus to studies.

Erjada Progonati and Farhad Gashamli's study titled "The Energy Geopolitics of Turkey-Azerbaijan Relations," which examines the importance of oil and natural gas pipelines between the two countries and their place in energy security, is noteworthy. (Progonati & Gashamli, 2021). This study addresses the energy issue specifically from a geopolitical perspective and evaluates it in this context.

Meanwhile, Bülent Aras's study titled "Turkish-Azerbaijani Energy Relations" outlines the development of energy cooperation between the two countries (Aras, 2014). The study titled "Economic and Political Analysis of Azerbaijan-Turkey Energy Relations" by Elçin Suleymanov, Cihan Bulut, and Farhad

Rahmanov presents a comparative analysis of the economic relations between Türkiye and Azerbaijan. (Süleymanov et al., 2017). In the literature, the most prominent discussion regarding Energy Security – Türkiye-Azerbaijan relations is that the energy relationship between the two countries is based on mutual dependence. For example, Şaban Kardaş argues in his study titled “Turkey-Azerbaijan Energy Partnership in the Context of the Southern Corridor” (2014) that there is a relationship of mutual dependence between Turkey and Azerbaijan (Kardaş, 2014). Similarly, in his study titled “Turkish-Azerbaijani Energy Cooperation and Nabucco: Testing the Limits of the New Turkish Foreign Policy Rhetoric,” he examines Turkish-Azerbaijani energy cooperation in detail in the context of the Nabucco natural gas pipeline (Kardaş, 2011). Similarly, Şaban Kardaş and Fatih Macit's study titled “Turkey-Azerbaijan Relations: The Economic Dimension” examines the economic ties between Türkiye and Azerbaijan. Economic factors are the main focus throughout the article.

A general assessment based on all these studies leads to the following conclusion: Türkiye's relations with Azerbaijan have generally been defined through events. A significant portion of the studies on Türkiye's energy relations with Azerbaijan lack a theoretical framework. Therefore, this study aims to examine the Türkiye-Azerbaijan energy relationship within the framework of neorealism. Some studies on energy security between Türkiye and Azerbaijan have evaluated the issue within the framework of interdependence and geopolitical approaches. These analyses primarily emphasize the strategic importance of pipelines and the economic dimension of energy relations between the two countries. In this context, the present study differs from similar studies in the existing literature by examining Türkiye-Azerbaijan energy relations from a new, realistic perspective. Since there is no academic study that directly addresses the energy relations between these two countries with a new, realistic approach, this thesis is expected to make a significant contribution to the literature.

This study primarily focuses on the neorealist approach to energy security, analyzes Azerbaijan-Türkiye energy relations within this framework, and then emphasizes Azerbaijan's importance for Türkiye's energy security.

2.THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 The Neorealist Approach to Energy Security

Neo-realist theory has long been at the center of the security debate within the discipline, and its discourse has been influenced by this. From its origins in Machiavelli and Hobbes to Morgenthau and classical realism, neo-realism continues to be popular within the discipline, with thinkers such as Waltz and Mearsheimer offering groundbreaking texts that discuss security in depth from a neo-realist perspective (Glaser, 2010:1). Thus, neorealists have frequently referred to the concept of security, bringing it to the fore. In particular, they have positioned the concept of security on top of the concept of anarchy, which is analyzed as the structure of the international system. Neorealism's view of security is based on the assumption that anarchy is the cause of competition between sovereign states in an international environment where there is no central authority. Furthermore, neorealism emphasizes material factors in shaping security policies. It suggests that the priority is to increase power to ensure the security of the state, which can be achieved by increasing material capacity and establishing a balance of power. In this context, when compared with other theories, neorealism is perhaps the theory within International Relations theories that attaches the most importance to the issue of security (Ağır, 2011: 101).

States that pursue power to ensure their security, fear other states, and know they operate in a self-sufficient world understand that the best way to survive is to be particularly powerful. The more powerful a state is compared to other states it competes with, the lower the likelihood of any external intervention. For example, no country in the Western Hemisphere dares to attack the United States because it is much more powerful than its neighbors (Mearsheimer, 2013: 80). In other words, powerful states seek to control the largest share of material resources, particularly military and economic assets, in their regions of the world. However, it is often overlooked that aggressive realism also suggests that powerful states try to influence and restrict the behavior of their smaller neighbors (Götz, 2016: 302). Major powers seeking to gain control over energy resources want to strengthen their position and ensure their energy security by entering these markets, where energy resources are consumed less. To this end, they also use their technological capabilities and economic superiority to steer global international relations by imposing sanctions on developing countries through arguments such as globalization, the new world order, the clash of civilizations, and/or new definitions of security (Bayraç, 2010: 121). For example, Azerbaijan, which gained independence after the dissolution of the USSR, is the only country that exports its energy resources to international markets outside Russian territory. Despite being an Eastern country, Azerbaijan aims to increase its revenue from energy resources

and strike a balance between the West and Russia in terms of escaping Russian pressure by maintaining good relations with Western states and multinational energy companies. However, this situation greatly disturbs Russia, which wants to maintain its energy dominance in the region (Erdoğan, 2017: 19). In particular, Russia uses its energy exports as a means of economic gain and as a foreign policy tool. At times, it has been seen to use its energy resources as a means of control and to exert political pressure. Regardless of the purpose, most authoritarian states rich in energy use their energy wealth to survive. Considering all these factors, the competition among states for energy resources becomes even clearer. Here, it should be noted that the basic parameters of the international energy regime are determined by the hegemonic powers.

As can be seen, the desire to acquire power stemming from the anarchic structure of the international system also determines how sovereign states should behave. The anarchic structure of the system is so powerful that common patterns of behavior emerge among units. In other words, anarchy produces similar units. In this anarchic international system, the fundamental goal of states is to ensure their survival. As a regulatory principle, the desire of states in an anarchic system to do whatever is necessary for their survival creates a competitive environment. Competition leads to imitation, and imitation leads to similarity. According to Waltz, no matter how different political units are from each other before interaction, the anarchic structure of the system leads to uniformity in the behavior of states (Yalvaç, 1996: 155). Therefore, states struggle in the same way to exist. However, there are differences between states in terms of fulfilling systemic functions. Each state has different capacities. Each state can fulfill its functions within its power. States strive to fulfill the functions imposed by the system in order to survive. This situation brings out the desire for power in states that want to fulfill their functions (Bozdağlıoğlu & Özen, 2004: 62). For example, when assessed in terms of energy security, countries outside the South Caucasus region focus on ensuring energy security and supply, exhibiting similar behaviors. Global powers are showing increasing interest in strategic regions where energy resources are located and in oil transportation routes. The interest of global and regional powers in these areas and the energy policies they implement in countries through which energy pipelines pass have turned these regions into focal points of global power struggles. In this context, the interventions of global powers aiming to establish influence in the region pave the way for instability. For example, the support given to Armenia by regional and global powers in line with their strategic interests in the South Caucasus has the potential to threaten energy security and stability in the region. Therefore, in this anarchic system where similar behaviors are exhibited, the desire to gain power increases the risk of conflict between sovereign states. However, the power of hegemonic states refers to military and economic power.

Neorealists do not view power solely as military and physical force. Although military capacity ranks first among other components of power, it is accepted that economic, geographical, and cultural elements are also important parameters that determine power, and that these components are used as tools for the purpose of obtaining military power (Güneş, 2012: 82). The primary issue that prompts Neorealists to consider the economic dimension of security as important as its military dimension is that military power does not always yield the desired results. The situation of the US, which lost the Vietnam War despite its military superiority, the Arab-Israeli Wars, and the subsequent 1973 Oil Crisis are among the best examples showing the consequences of states prioritizing military power and neglecting economic power. These wars showed states that military power alone is not sufficient to achieve their goals. Prioritizing the enhancement of military parameters alone demonstrates the importance of also considering economic parameters (Özdoğan, 2019: 9). Therefore, energy wars and oil crises indicate that states must consider the interaction between the economy and the military in order to achieve their objectives in line with their interests, and that economic indicators must be taken into account alongside military power. States that possess both military and economic power can eventually gain the ability to manage other states and control them according to their wishes (Şöhret, 2012: 302). Similarly, countries with high energy capacity have a direct or indirect influence on energy-deficient countries and energy transmission lines. States that possess economic power elements such as energy are in a relatively superior position in the economic system (Kökyay, 2020: 2513).

Energy resources are, in a sense, one of the important conditions for a state to have a strong economy. However, while energy resources have a positive impact on the economy on the one hand, it is also clear that energy conflicts and wars damage the economies of states on the other. Ultimately, energy is a source of conflict because sectors that are vital for countries, such as energy, can harm the security of dependent states. From a neorealist perspective, major powers such as Russia, which hold economic power such as energy, shape the international system. While Russia uses its natural gas resources as a means of political pressure to exploit the energy resources in the South Caucasus region and maintain control over this strategic geography, another global power, the US, is developing alternative energy routes and striving to establish

various alliances in order to break Russia's monopoly in the energy sector. Therefore, these powers are shaping energy-rich regions in line with their national interests and creating an environment of conflict.

Neorealists argue that energy, a strategically vital element, is not only a national security issue but also part of states' foreign policies. National interests play a major role in determining energy policies. States will try to ensure energy security on their own. State interests will guide decisions regarding energy policies. When it comes to securing energy imports, bilateral supply agreements will take precedence over multilateral agreements. From a neorealist perspective, the emerging picture is one where national interests prevail and self-help is pursued through bilateral supply agreements. The neorealist view that nationalist sentiments prevail among importing states is combined with the view that the problem of supply security cannot be solved by markets alone (Elving, 2014: 10). At this point, although neorealism emphasizes the absence of an authority regulating the international system and presents a security perspective based on conflict and competition, it does not disregard the process of cooperation in ensuring security (Sandıklı and Emeklier 9). States may sometimes choose to form alliances when necessary to survive threats. However, states still have no choice but to put their own interests ahead of those of other states and the so-called international community. Ultimately, states must always rely on themselves to ensure their survival because the intentions of other states are uncertain.

In an environment where states' intentions are uncertain, there is no higher authority they can turn to when attacked. However, states can still form alliances that are useful for dealing with dangerous enemies (Mearsheimer, 2013: 80). At this point, Türkiye is pursuing various policy strategies to balance supply and demand in order to ensure energy security. Türkiye is keen on cooperation in the energy sector in line with its national interests in order to increase its power and thus ensure its security. Based on the assumption that the anarchic international system inevitably leads to power struggles, which in turn drives states to increase their power, cooperation in the energy sector is crucial for Türkiye and Azerbaijan to maximize their power in order to ensure their security in their desire to survive in the anarchic international system. The existing pipeline projects between the two countries are also projects that increase their economic power. At this point, the fact that they act together in the process of delivering Azerbaijan's energy resources safely and uninterruptedly to countries in need through international energy projects such as BTC, BTE, and TANAP shows that they have established close cooperation in this area. In conclusion, Türkiye chooses temporary cooperation and alliances to increase its insufficient energy capacity, ensure its security, and prevent threats to its national interests.

In an anarchic international system, the distribution of power capacities is unequal, so states in a disadvantaged position seek to balance their power. This, in turn, leads to the establishment of a cooperative order (Balcı 134). However, no matter how much cooperation there is, in a competitive, insecure, and anarchic international system, a state's goal is always to consider its own interests. Relative gain, rather than the absolute gain emphasized by neoliberals, is important for neorealists. Relative gain gives rise to the desire to protect one's own interests and be in a superior position to others. When states cooperate with other states, they consider how powerful they are relative to others rather than whether it is beneficial for both sides. Since all states desire to increase their gains, choosing and maintaining cooperation will not always be easy (Baylis, 2008: 75). The main goal of power balance theory is to protect the integrity of the multi-state system by preventing an ambitious state from swallowing up its neighbors. The fundamental understanding behind the theory is that states should not be trusted with excessive power that threatens all members of the international system. The danger here is that a predatory great power could seize more than half of the system's total resources and thus be in a position to subjugate everything else (Schweller, 2016: 4).

Russia's stance in the Azerbaijan–Armenia crisis serves as a good example in this regard. Russia prioritizes its own interests in the South Caucasus region. Seeking to maintain the balance of power when necessary, Russia acts as an arbitrator between states in line with its interests. Through its role as an arbitrator in resolving the conflict and the power balance system it has established, Russia aims to keep both the region and both sides under its control. When deemed necessary, it does not assume all responsibility itself but shares it with regional states it cooperates with, as in the case of Türkiye. With this strategy, it seeks to prevent threats that may come from regional and global actors towards the South Caucasus region. In this regard, it aims to keep Armenia, which opposes its authority, under control by supporting a strengthening Azerbaijan and restraining Armenia with Azerbaijan (Nagiyev, 2021: 89). Türkiye, which wants to maintain a balance of power when necessary, is not in a position to compete with Russia in energy. Therefore, in order to ensure energy security and create diversity of sources, it has decided to enter into economic cooperation with Azerbaijan, which has high capacity, to balance the power of this country. Ultimately, because it does not know Russia's intentions regarding energy, it chooses the path of power balance to prevent potential

threats from Russia. At this point, another example of balancing is that regional states, worn down by the struggle between Russia's encirclement policy and the West trying to prevent it, prioritize their relations with Türkiye in order to maintain a balance between these powers.

States ultimately want to know whether other states intend to use force (revisionist states) or are sufficiently satisfied that they have no interest in using force to change it (status quo states) in an environment where they do not know the intentions of other states. However, the problem is that it is impossible to know a state's true intentions. Unlike military capabilities, intentions cannot be empirically verified. Intentions reside in the minds of decision-makers and are particularly difficult to discern (Mearsheimer, 2013: 79). A neighbor may appear to be a status quo power, but in reality be a revisionist state. Or it may be a status quo situation today, but change its lines tomorrow. In an anarchic system with no ultimate arbiter, states seeking to survive must assume the worst possible scenario because they cannot be certain about other states' intentions and must know that they have few options other than competing with them for power. This is the tragedy of great power politics (Mearsheimer, 2013: 80). However, even though states cannot be certain about the intentions of other states, states are rational actors, which means that they can apply the recipes they use to survive in the most accurate way possible. This argument does not mean that they never make miscalculations. Because states sometimes make big mistakes in a complex world. However, what is important here is that states act rationally and logically for their national interests (Mearsheimer, 2013: 79). In this context, when Türkiye and Azerbaijan's energy relations are considered, both sides act with the desire to protect their own national interests. Therefore, in the policies pursued in the energy relations between the two countries, both states act rationally and logically.

States are concerned about the intentions of other states. Ultimately, there is very little trust between states. Their greatest fear is that another state has both the capability and the motivation to attack them. This danger is compounded by the fact that states operate in an anarchic system, meaning that when threatened by another state, they have no guardian to come to their rescue. When a state calls the emergency line, there is no one in the international system to answer (Mearsheimer, 2013: 79). Waltz argues that the main cause of war and conflict stems from the structure of the international system. According to Waltz, the absence of a superstate in the international system gives rise to the system's anarchic structure. Neorealism, like realism, emphasizes the existence of a desire for power stemming from the anarchic structure of the international system rather than from a desire for power stemming from the evil nature of man (Yalvaç, 1996: 150). According to this prediction of neo-realism, the absence of a supreme authority in the energy field, i.e., the absence of an organization that would guarantee energy security and policies, will give rise to the desire to gain power by providing access to energy resources among states. This will increase the risk of conflict.

Another concept introduced by neorealism, conflict and competition, comes into play at this point. In an international system without central authority over states, where there is no reason for one not to attack another, it is only common sense for each state to want to be strong enough to defend itself against attacks. Essentially, if they want to survive, they must compete with each other (Mearsheimer, 2013: 79). This anarchic structure of the international system gives rise to the desire to acquire power, and this desire leads to competition among the states in the system. All these necessities are reflected in the concept of the security dilemma. The security dilemma means that every step a state takes to ensure its own security will pose a threat to the security of other states. One side's desire to ensure its security creates a feeling of insecurity on the other side. For example, a state seeking to strengthen its position in the international system will seek to increase its power despite the relative power loss of other states. It is quite difficult for a state to improve its conditions for survival without posing a threat to other states. At a certain point, one state's desire to gain power will threaten the survival of another state. However, states under threat will do whatever is necessary to ensure their survival and will threaten other states in return. All of this leads to a perpetual security competition (Mearsheimer, 2013: 80). For example, it has become a region where conflict and competition are seen between global actors such as Russia and the US, which have interests in energy resources and seek to establish dominance over the region, as well as regional actors such as Türkiye and Iran. In this context, Azerbaijan's rise in the energy sector and its efforts to bypass Russia and deliver its energy resources to the West are perceived as a threat by Russia. Russia, which views the South Caucasus as its backyard, does not want its rival, the US, to play an active role in the region. This competition also shapes the energy policies of these countries with interests in the region. Consequently, states that are key actors in the international system view each other as potential threats. This situation is one of the concrete examples of the security dilemma.

As a result, the power struggle between regional and global powers in South Caucasus can be analyzed from a neo-realist perspective. The competition between Russia and the US, both seeking to dominate energy resources in the South Caucasus and gain a larger share of these resources, can be interpreted as a power struggle. Russia's rational security policies towards the South Caucasus, aimed at dominating energy resources, and the competition between these two powers over this region are also points that should be considered within the framework of neorealism. The emphasis on the importance of power in international relations, the assumption that the cause of competition and conflict in bilateral relations stems from the anarchic structure of the international system, and the assumption that, due to this anarchic structure of the international system, the only concern of states is how to guarantee their survival, are the basis of neorealist arguments. It is possible to say that at least a large part of these arguments are valid for Türkiye -Azerbaijan energy security relations and can be applied to developments in the South Caucasus region where these states are located. The South Caucasus region, which includes Azerbaijan as the source country and Georgia and Armenia as transit routes for pipelines, holds a significant geopolitical position. Türkiye, located on an important geopolitical axis, is at the center of regional and global power struggles in the region. Due to its geopolitical position, Türkiye may be affected by the problems of this region in which it is involved.

3. AZERBAIJAN'S IMPORTANCE IN TÜRKİYE'S ENERGY SECURITY

3.1. Türkiye as an Energy Transit Corridor

Should Türkiye be considered an energy hub or an energy bridge, or should another definition be used? This question is one of the most frequently asked questions in the energy sector in recent years. To describe Türkiye's position in energy trade, terms such as energy bridge, transit country, and hub country have been used at certain times. Recently, with the increase in international projects where Türkiye plays a role as a transit country, Türkiye is mostly defined as a transit country (Yılmaz, 2021: 43).

Due to its geographical location, Türkiye hosts a large portion of energy pipelines. These pipelines are of geopolitical importance, positioning Türkiye as an energy transit country. Türkiye, a critical market for energy transmission from Asia to Europe and from the Middle East to Europe, aims to further strengthen its position through pipeline agreements. Ultimately, countries must import energy from reliable sources via secure routes in order to ensure sustainable development (Harunoğulları, 6). At this point, it has been observed that Türkiye is a preferred transit country for energy producers due to various factors, such as its important role in Europe's energy security. This position also shapes its energy relations with its neighbors.

Türkiye's close neighbors, which possess oil and natural gas resources, wish to use Türkiye as a transit country to deliver their energy resources to European markets. Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, Russia, Iran, the Kurdish Region of Northern Iraq, and even countries in the Eastern Mediterranean prefer Türkiye for this purpose (Altundeğer, 2015: 75). Türkiye's goal of transporting energy resources, particularly from the Caspian Region, to European countries as an energy distribution hub will enable Caspian Region countries to profit from the European energy market while reducing European countries' dependence on Russian gas imports. At the same time, this situation contributes to Türkiye's goal of becoming an energy hub, while also enabling it to import oil and gas resources from energy-rich countries and establish close relations with them. Thus, it creates a win-win situation for both sides (Kakışım, 2019: 77). The projects Türkiye has undertaken with its neighbors help strengthen its position as an energy corridor.

The TANAP and TurkStream projects are helping Türkiye achieve this goal. If Türkiye can achieve a central position in natural gas sales, it can benefit from TurkStream. The TurkStream project appears to prevent supply security problems that may arise after the Russia-Ukraine conflict, both for the EU and Türkiye. Furthermore, this project will also ensure Russia's demand security. Unlike the Turkish Stream project, the TANAP project is an alternative to Russian gas. It has the potential to reduce the EU and Türkiye's dependence on Russia. Furthermore, the fact that regional energy resources can also be transported via this pipeline is one of the factors that makes the project important. These pipeline projects carried out by Türkiye with Azerbaijan and Russia will be an important step towards making Türkiye an energy hub in the long term (Yılmaz, 2021: 42). As can be seen, Türkiye strongly supports pipeline projects and is strengthening its position as a transit country with these completed or ongoing projects. The transit fees generated from these projects will make significant contributions to Türkiye's economy. The existence of pipelines also enables Türkiye to secure uninterrupted, affordable, and reliable energy sources. This plays a critical role in ensuring Türkiye's energy security. Such projects position Türkiye as an important stepping stone on the path to achieving its goal of becoming a multi-faceted energy corridor. Furthermore, Türkiye will also gain the opportunity to increase its regional influence through control of energy routes. In short, its position as a

transit country is a fundamental factor shaping Türkiye's energy policies (Esen, 2016: 287). In addition, Türkiye is an important energy transit hub not only in terms of pipelines but also in maritime trade.

The Turkish Straits also highlight Türkiye's position as an energy transit region. The Bosphorus and Dardanelles Straits are critical waterways separating Asia from Europe. The Bosphorus is a 27-kilometer waterway connecting the Black Sea to the Sea of Marmara. The Dardanelles Strait is a 40-mile waterway connecting the Sea of Marmara to the Aegean and Mediterranean Seas. The Turkish Straits are of critical importance for transporting oil from Russia and the Caspian Sea region to Western and Southern Europe. As of 2016, the daily amount of oil and natural gas passing through the Turkish Straits is around 2.4 million barrels, more than 80% of which is crude oil. Ports on the Black Sea are among the important oil export routes for other Eurasian countries, primarily Russia, Azerbaijan, and Kazakhstan (EIA, 2017: 12). As can be seen, Türkiye is a country that acts as a bridge for energy transfer between energy-rich regions and energy-importing countries and aims to become an energy hub. For this to happen, Türkiye needs to diversify its sources in order to become an energy hub as a current importer and reach the level of an exporter. This source diversity includes large storage capacities and trading centers built in national and international regions. Under current conditions, Türkiye cannot be defined as an energy hub due to a lack of investments and strategic plans, the absence of large oil and natural gas reserves, the lack of suitable storage facilities, and restrictions in existing energy agreements (Akyener & Apaydın, 2016: 33).

3.2. Reducing Russian Influence and Dependency

The energy sector has traditionally been an important part of the Russian economy. A large part of Russia's economy relies on revenues from oil and gas exports. In 2011, Russia generated more than 67% of its export revenues from energy. Consequently, revenues from the sector account for more than half of the budget. In short, Russia has been accumulating foreign exchange reserves from energy exports in recent years (Mitorova 9 According to the latest report published by the Energy Market Regulatory Authority, Russia was Türkiye's leading natural gas importer in 2023 with 21.340 million cubic meters. The second largest importer was Azerbaijan with 10.257 million cubic meters. Iran, Algeria, and the USA are also among the countries from which Türkiye imports natural gas. Therefore, in 2023, 39.4% of Türkiye's imported natural gas came from Russia, 17.2% from Iran, and 15.9% from Azerbaijan (EPDK, 2024a: 15). In 2023, approximately 51.1% of Türkiye's imported oil came from Russia, with only 0.1% coming from Azerbaijan (EPDK, 2024b :7). Therefore, a large part of Türkiye's energy consumption is supplied by Russia. Thus, it can be seen that Türkiye has advanced its relations with Russia, its largest hydrocarbon supplier over the years, in order to meet its energy demand. However, this relationship has also brought with it a high degree of dependence on Russia.

Such dependence on a single energy source, supplier, or supply route creates economic and political risks. In the event of any dispute, dependence on a single source or producer can cause economic and social turmoil that is difficult to rectify and compensate for. From this perspective, in order to ensure energy security, a supply chain should be established with various sources from different suppliers. Problems experienced by Türkiye in its natural gas and oil supply due to tensions in the Middle East (such as Syria and Iraq) or between Ukraine and Russia (this also applies to all European countries that are net energy importers) have brought the issue of energy security back to the agenda. These problems highlight Türkiye's dependence on only a few energy sources and the possibility that this dependence will increase. Therefore, the damage that a possible interruption in the supply of these resources could cause to the economy is clear (Esen, 2016: 284). It is also possible that Russia, as the dependent party, may impose supply cuts on Türkiye or use energy as a political tool. This situation can lead to much higher costs for the more dependent party than for the more powerful party. At this point, Türkiye is establishing energy partnerships with projects that both meet its own needs and reduce its dependence on Russia. It is likely that Türkiye will further increase its cooperation with Azerbaijan to reduce its dependence on Russian gas. In this context, Türkiye is expected to take action with new partnerships.

In line with this goal, Türkiye is focusing on energy cooperation with Azerbaijan. By facilitating the delivery of Azerbaijani natural gas to the European market via pipelines, Türkiye will gain several advantages. First, it will move a step closer to its goal of becoming an energy hub. Furthermore, projects such as TANAP, which strengthen Türkiye-Azerbaijan cooperation and reduce Russian pressure, will ensure diversification of sources and routes, thereby securing energy supply. By ensuring diversity in energy sources to minimize dependence on a single market, country, or region and to ensure uninterrupted energy supply, Türkiye will gain a strategic advantage over Russia in the global energy market (Merdan, 2021: 466). Ultimately, Türkiye is dissatisfied with Russia's policy of filling the power vacuum in the Caucasus and Central Asia and its

intervention in these countries. However, due to its natural gas agreements with Russia and its energy dependence on it, Türkiye refrains from pursuing an anti-Russian policy. Türkiye occupies a very important position because it is right in the middle of the competition between the West and Russia over pipeline routes. In addition, Türkiye is strategically positioned as virtually the only route for Europe to access the energy-rich Caspian and Central Asian regions. For the Caspian region states, Türkiye also contributes to the development of their relations with the West by providing them with access to Western markets. Thus, it also helps the countries in the region to free themselves from Russian pressure. All these advantageous circumstances also increase Türkiye's political power (Turan, 2010: 64). Aware of these opportunities in the Caspian region, Türkiye is cooperating with the countries in the region and undertaking various initiatives. With these initiatives, Türkiye aims to reduce its vulnerability in case Russia uses its energy card. It aims to minimize the negative consequences that dependence on a single country would bring in the event of a crisis or conflict (Kakışım, 2019: 83).

Russia and Türkiye can easily reduce their dependence on each other as they are close to other energy suppliers and customers. For example, in the event of a possible supply disruption, Türkiye can replace its demand from Azerbaijan, Iran, or Iraq, while Russia can replace its supply from Europe or Asia in the event of termination of the agreement (Akgül, 2019: 113). However, the fact that the amount of natural gas imported from Russia is very high and that the additional natural gas that can be obtained from other supplier countries in a short time would be insufficient to cover the energy gap that could arise if Russia cuts off its natural gas flow should not be overlooked (Kakışım, 2019: 83). Therefore, in terms of the resource diversification approach, Türkiye does not want to antagonize Russia. Türkiye's stance has alleviated Russia's concerns and enabled Türkiye and Azerbaijan to continue their energy partnerships without antagonizing Russia. With this new understanding, Azerbaijan has succeeded in exporting not only its oil but also its gas to Western markets on its own terms. However, if Türkiye or European actors refocus on the TCP or other projects and exert pressure to include Turkmen gas, competitive dynamics with Russia may reemerge. In such a scenario, closer strategic dialogue and policy coordination between Western actors and the Türkiye-Azerbaijan duo would be an urgent necessity (Kardaş, 2014: 9).

Russia, on the other hand, effectively uses its energy power as a foreign policy tool and aims to maintain its monopoly position on energy routes. For this reason, it has chosen to increase source diversification and determine different routes for energy. Diversification, in particular, is one of the most important aspects of Russia's energy policy. Russia does not look favorably upon the BTC Pipeline, which transports Azerbaijani and Kazakh oil to Western markets without Russia's involvement, or the Nabucco Project, which aims to transport Caspian energy resources to European markets via a new East-West corridor. Furthermore, in addition to not looking favorably upon these projects that bypass it, Russia is developing new projects to challenge them. The Nord Stream and South Stream projects were developed with this objective in mind (Özbay, 2011: 60). With these projects, Russia plans to access energy markets outside Europe, increase energy security by diversifying energy transmission routes in Europe, avoid being affected by the problems of transit countries, and balance costs by constructing new natural gas pipelines.

In conclusion, at this point, influenced by the neorealist argument that powerful states pursue aggressive policies, Türkiye is taking steps to reduce its dependence on a country like Russia, which can use energy as a bargaining chip. In a system dominated by chaos, the first and foremost goal of both states is to ensure energy security. From a neorealist perspective, the uncertainty of each state's future intentions and actions and the desire to secure national interests give rise to the desire for alliances and cooperation with other actors. Türkiye seeks to balance its power by cooperating with Azerbaijan, which it perceives as strong against Russia. Ultimately, states must secure their energy resources through safe and uninterrupted channels. In an anarchic system, states must strive to survive. They must ensure their security to sustain their existence. This compels states to seek power. Therefore, Azerbaijan's rich energy resources, by providing Türkiye with energy sources, increase Türkiye's economic power and, by diversifying its source countries, reduce its dependence on a single country and minimize threats that may come from Russia. As a state's energy resources increase, its power increases proportionally. While states such as Türkiye strive for security, major powers such as Russia seek to expand their power. In the energy relationship between Azerbaijan and Türkiye, there are conflicts of interest between Türkiye and Russia regarding energy interests. From the perspective of neorealism, which assumes that states cannot know what rival states think about them and will therefore be suspicious, the Türkiye-Azerbaijan relationship is perceived as a threat by Russia. The conflicting national interests of states fuel competition over resources. In short, both countries' desire to meet their energy needs creates a security dilemma. However, Azerbaijan does not ignore Russia in every step it

takes in the energy field. At this point, the most important argument for Russia and Türkiye is their national interests.

3.3. Secure Cooperation

Energy affects many areas, from politics to industry, agriculture to health, transportation to communications, and international relations. Energy, one of the factors that influence and shape international relations, is particularly noteworthy in terms of cooperation between countries. This cooperation is shaped by many factors, both internal and external. These include economic, political, and social factors. In addition, factors such as geographical location, security, imperial perceptions, technological developments, climate change, political and economic crises, regional conflicts, and occupations must also be considered when determining strategies for energy cooperation (Ulusaler, 2012: 52). Through cooperation based on all these factors, states come together within a network. Thus, through cooperation, they ensure their energy security, which is vital for their national security.

Energy security is directly proportional to countries' national security. Failure to ensure security creates a survival problem for countries. Any disruption in a country's energy supply has the potential to negatively impact many areas, including political, military, economic, and socio-cultural aspects. For this reason, in the 21st century, states must cooperate with countries that import, export, and transfer energy in order to ensure their own energy security. Otherwise, no country can guarantee its energy security alone. The national security of a country whose energy security is not guaranteed is at risk (Özalp, 2018: 24). However, this threat can be eliminated through strong energy cooperation between producer and consumer countries. States seeking to ensure their national security also attach importance to energy diversity when determining their energy strategies. Ultimately, producer states ensure their economic development through energy resources. They also diversify their buyer countries to ensure continuous and stable economic development. Energy-deficient energy-importing states are also seeking source diversity. In the event of a future economic or political crisis, energy-importing countries will not face the risk of energy shortages. Producing countries will also be able to generate income from energy without being dependent on a single consumer. In this way, countries ensure their energy security. This goal creates an environment for cooperation between energy-rich countries and global and regional powers (Turan, 2010: 46). Moreover, these collaborations have the potential to increase stability in the region. Energy is also a factor that influences diplomatic relations. The conciliatory decisions that these countries will make by prioritizing the energy sector in the face of many political problems they encounter will bring the region to the forefront in energy trade (Karagöl and Özdemir, 2017: 15).

Energy-rich Azerbaijan and energy-importing Türkiye continue to maintain close cooperation through the projects they have implemented. This cooperation directly or indirectly benefits many countries as importers, exporters, and carriers in the process of delivering the energy resources of a reserve-rich country like Azerbaijan to countries that need them continuously and reliably (Memmedli and Pınar 236). Furthermore, Türkiye is involved in Azerbaijan's issues in the Caucasus. Thus, the rapprochement between Türkiye and Azerbaijan in the energy sector has created a favorable environment not only economically but also politically. The energy cooperation that began between Türkiye and Azerbaijan, which are positioned as a bridge between East and West, has become a priority, and both countries aim to further strengthen their relations by entering into strategic partnerships in line with their interests in the energy sector through many projects such as the BTC oil pipeline and the BTE natural gas pipeline (Erdoğan, 2017: 18-19). Türkiye continues its strategic investments in the energy sector in line with its common strategic goals with Azerbaijan. One of the most recent steps taken in this direction is TANAP, which is highly important for diversifying the energy supply points of Türkiye and the European Union. In addition, a petroleum refinery has been built with Petkim, a project carried out by SOCAR, one of Azerbaijan's major energy companies. This plant was realized with SOCAR's \$6.3 billion investment. Petkim, built with major investments in the Turkish economy, will strengthen both the Azerbaijani and Turkish economies. These collaborations between the two countries in the energy sector also give rise to cooperation in many areas, including trade, transportation, and politics. For example, the BTK railway, completed in 2017, is an important step towards advancing cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye and between Azerbaijan and Georgia and combining economic interests. This project is seen as a step towards facilitating trade and transportation between these countries. It is also a project that aims to increase freight and passenger traffic flows through the two countries and advance regional cooperation (T.C Ticaret Bakanlığı, 2022: 6).

The friendship and cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye have entered a new phase with the Second Karabakh War. Since Türkiye and Azerbaijan are linked by ethnic ties, Ankara pledged to support its ally on the battlefield and at the negotiating table, and this has been the case in the Second Karabakh War. Although there have been ups and downs in the relations between Erdoğan and Aliyev during the twenty years of the Justice and Development Party's rule in Ankara, Azerbaijan has recently emerged as an important economic and military partner for Türkiye. Türkiye appears set to remain the main channel for Azerbaijan's oil and gas exports (Aydıntaşbaş and Girogasyon, 2022: 9). Furthermore, the tripartite ceasefire agreement that ended the Second Karabakh War and the opening of the Zangezur Corridor, a strategically important passageway between Azerbaijan, Türkiye, and other Turkic states, appear to be taking cooperation between the two countries to a higher level. This corridor will provide Türkiye with a shorter route to the Turkic states in Central Asia and China. The opening of the Zangezur Corridor will generally enable Türkiye to gain a stronger foothold in the region. Ultimately, the opening of the Zangezur Corridor will be beneficial in allowing Türkiye to take advantage of an even shorter route to Central Asia, mostly passing through the territories of Turkic states. The establishment of a new corridor will create opportunities for further expansion of economic relations between Azerbaijan and Türkiye. The fact that the Zengezur Corridor is actually another route bypassing Russia in the strategically important South Caucasus indicates that it is a project that Russia does not view favorably. Therefore, delaying or blocking the opening of the corridor, which will initiate this process, is in Russia's interests. The Zengezur Corridor is expected to play an active role in international relations and regional cooperation projects (Yüce, 2022: 107-108).

The Alliance Declaration signed by the presidents of the two countries in Shusha, the cradle of Azerbaijani culture and a place of great importance for Azerbaijan, is seen as a new bilateral roadmap encompassing political and economic cooperation (including energy, trade, and other areas), with the aim of elevating bilateral relations between Türkiye and Azerbaijan to the level of an alliance. The Shusha Declaration is an important document in terms of strengthening Azerbaijan's regional geopolitical position, deepening and diversifying Türkiye's bilateral cooperation with Azerbaijan, strengthening its regional geopolitical position, and providing additional security guarantees in the unstable South Caucasus (Shahbazov, 2021: 1).

In this context, the mutual needs and interests between the two countries require Türkiye to continue cooperating with Azerbaijan and supporting each other in the future. In addition to cooperating with Azerbaijan to ensure energy security, Azerbaijan also needs Türkiye, just as Türkiye plays an important role in helping Azerbaijan deliver its energy resources to Western markets and avoid Russia's dominance. Furthermore, Türkiye's cooperation with countries such as Georgia in the energy sector is also important and forms the Türkiye-Georgia-Azerbaijan axis in terms of security. This axis creates a security belt for ensuring stability and regional security in the South Caucasus. This secure cooperation in the energy sector within the Türkiye-Georgia-Azerbaijan axis demonstrates the support for regional cooperation and the development of relations to a strategic partnership level (Ekşi, 2009: 9).

In summary, Neo-Realist theory can be both competitive and cooperative. The theory manifests itself in different ways in different contexts. While considering the broad framework of security, structural necessity compels states to compete for security. However, applying the theory in the context of energy security yields more cooperative results. Today, the international energy system is bipolar in structure and remains stable and peaceful. Therefore, within the framework of energy security, the neo-realist understanding encourages cooperation rather than competition (Jaybhay, 2020). The factor that determines whether states choose cooperation or competition is their interests. Both actors must protect their security and national interests in an anarchic international system. Ensuring their survival is one of their greatest goals. In order to achieve this goal, Türkiye and Azerbaijan choose cooperation to ensure their security by acting rationally in line with their interests. Both countries aim to reduce security vulnerabilities. Azerbaijan generates economic gains by exporting a significant portion of its resources. For countries like Türkiye, Azerbaijan represents an important opportunity to maximize their interests in the energy sector and achieve economic and political gains. Ultimately, any power gained economically will also permeate the political sphere. Türkiye's choice of cooperation to ensure its energy security is indicative of its desire to serve its national interests and increase its power and security. In short, Türkiye and Azerbaijan have chosen cooperation in the energy sector to serve their national interests, opting for a policy that enhances their power and security. In this context, it is rational for both actors, aiming to maximize the benefits they will obtain from the resources, to develop policies to protect their national interests. Türkiye has acted rationally in its foreign policy, aiming to strengthen its relations with dominant states in the system, such as Azerbaijan. The basis of the energy policy of the two countries is cooperation based on mutual benefit.

4.CONCLUSION

The South Caucasus is a region of strategic importance in terms of energy resources, but it is also a region where the global power struggle is clearly evident. The desire to control the region's energy resources and maximize their use lies at the heart of the competition between international powers. Global actors prioritize their national interests in their activities in this region, which further reinforces the anarchic structure of the international system and the quest for power. In this context, as emphasized by neo-realists, actors in the international system must act out of necessity to protect their own security and national interests under anarchic conditions. The desire to gain power in the context of an anarchic international system increases competition among states and heightens the risk of conflict between sovereign states. The region's unresolved and ongoing ethnic conflicts fuel geopolitical instability, which can negatively affect the stability of energy exports from energy-rich countries.

This situation has the potential to jeopardize the energy supply security of consumer countries seeking energy cooperation. Therefore, ensuring regional stability and increasing energy cooperation is essential for the secure and sustainable supply of energy resources. Despite being located in a region close to areas rich in oil and natural gas reserves, Türkiye does not have sufficient natural resources to meet its growing energy demand. This situation forces the country to meet a large portion of its energy needs through imports, making Türkiye dependent on foreign sources for energy. The country imports most of its oil and natural gas needs. Its largest supplier in this area is Russia. Being so heavily dependent on a single country or source carries both political and economic risks. Diversifying imported energy sources has become essential to reduce these risks and ensure energy security. Türkiye has turned to alternative energy supply routes to reduce its heavy dependence on Russia, and Azerbaijan is considered an important option in this context.

At this point, Azerbaijan stands out as a strong and stable partner in the energy sector, playing a significant role in Türkiye's strategies to enhance its energy security. In this context, it makes meaningful contributions to Türkiye's efforts to diversify its energy sources and helps the country gradually reduce its dependence on Russian natural gas. Furthermore, the implemented pipeline projects position Türkiye in a crucial position in global energy transfer and strategically position it as an energy transit corridor in the regional and international arena. Therefore, these collaborations and projects pave the way for strengthening relations between the two countries by enabling the evaluation of existing opportunities and the shaping of long-term energy goals. In this way, it is seen that the economic dimension alleviates security concerns.

Türkiye has demonstrated an open attitude toward cooperation in line with its national interests in the energy sector. Within the framework of the assumption that the anarchic international system inevitably paves the way for power struggles and that this situation leads states to seek to increase their own power, Türkiye and Azerbaijan have adopted energy cooperation as an important strategy for ensuring their survival and security. The existing pipeline projects between the two countries have not only an energy security dimension but also an economic power-enhancing dimension. In this context, in an international system without a central government, states must ensure their own security. At this point, Türkiye, influenced by the neorealist argument that powerful states pursue aggressive policies, is taking steps to reduce its dependence on a country like Russia, which can use energy as a bargaining chip. Thus, an examination of energy relations between Türkiye and Azerbaijan reveals that both sides are acting to protect their national interests. It can be said that the policies applied to energy cooperation between the two countries are shaped by a rational approach from both states. At this point, it can be concluded that the energy policies of Türkiye and Azerbaijan are consistent with the fundamental arguments of neorealism.

In conclusion, considering national interests, the anarchic nature of the international system, conflict and competition, the desire to be strong enough to defend oneself against all kinds of attacks, the importance of power in international relations, and the importance given to interstate economic relations, it has been determined that approaching the Azerbaijan-Türkiye energy relationship within the framework of neorealism in international relations theories is more appropriate.

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